

A Clinical Tutorial on Using a Concurrent Operant Analysis in the Assessment and Treatment of Problem Behavior

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- In addition to this COA Tutorial Presentation, several corresponding files can be found in the data repository. Please refer to the list below to assist with locating of materials in the repository.
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Instructions

- The purpose of this presentation is to assist with a self-guided tutorial and assessment for the article: “A Clinical Tutorial on Using a Concurrent Operant Analysis in the Assessment and Treatment of Problem Behavior.”
- The sequence of this slideshow includes an introduction, detailed steps for the COA, and vignette examples presented in the article.
- We recommend progressing through this presentation in conjunction with the article for best potential learning outcomes.
- Finally, you will see a self-assessment tool and novel example for application practice.

Step-by-Step Tutorial

Introduction

- Function-based treatments based on FAs lead to better treatment outcomes compared to those not based on FAs.
- Although barriers exist to completing FAs, many published resources are available for navigating modifications to FAs.
- Even with modifications, some reasons may prevent using FAs.

Introduction

- Concurrent operant analysis (COAs) is a direct experimental assessment that identifies reinforcers for choice-making behavior.
- COAs can not identify functional reinforcers maintaining problem behavior.
- Yet, a COA is more favorable to arbitrarily selecting reinforcers to use in the treatments for problem behavior.

Introduction

- COAs use a simultaneous-treatments experimental design in which concurrently available reinforcers are presented.
- Choice allocation is measured in duration of spent in the available conditions.
- The purpose of this tutorial is to provide a step-by-step outline with hypothetical case examples to assist with acquisition of a repertoire for considering, implementing, and analyzing COAs.

Clinical Tutorial Steps

- Step 1: Decide to Conduct a COA
- Step 2: Determine Location, Arrangement, Implementers and Materials
- Step 3: Develop COA Test Conditions
- Step 4: Create COA Test Comparisons
- Step 5: Select *a priori* Decision Rules and Procedures
- Step 6: Conduct COA Comparisons and Conduct Formative Analysis
- Step 7: Graphing, Visual Inspection, and Conclusions

Step 1: Decide to Conduct a COA

- We recommend considering a COA when either of the following conclusions has been met.
- Reason 1: An FA is Not Feasible
 - We explicitly encourage a practitioner to consider an FA
 - An FA may not be possible due to concerns about safety and expertise, as well as prohibitive policies
- Reason 2: An FA Does Not Produce Differentiated Outcomes
 - We explicitly encourage a practitioner to modify FAs as needed to achieve differentiated outcomes
 - An FA may yield undifferentiated outcomes following no or very low levels of problem behavior

Step 2: Determine Location, Arrangement, Implementers and Materials

- Select Location
 - Select a location that has sufficient space to move from condition to condition and can be used for several, at minimum, 5-min sessions
- Select Arrangement and Choice Measurement
 - Depending on location, arrange materials on either side of a room, desk, or partitioned area
 - Measure choice by a single response (e.g., selection of one side by moving body towards a side of a desk) and duration (e.g., time allocation to one side)
 - Use discriminative stimuli to signal each condition based matched to client needs

Step 2: Determine Location, Arrangement, Implementers and Materials

- Select Implementers
 - Select individuals whose attention you suspect is reinforcing for the client
 - Select individuals whose attention suspect the client may wish to avoid or escape
- Select Materials
 - Use materials indicated in a preference assessment or indirect interviews

Step 3: Develop COA Test Conditions

- Develop narrative condition descriptions that include the potential hypotheses and arrangements of reinforcers maintaining challenging behavior
 - Example: Condition A includes a preferred therapist and access to an iPad equipped with Minecraft
- Identify stimulus classes within the narrative descriptions, including potential aversive stimuli
 - Example: Condition A: high-preferred attention and tangibles

Step 4: Create COA Test Comparisons

- Consider Constant Variables and Test Variables
- Constant and Test Variables are subject to change *depending* on the specific COA condition pairing.
- **Constant Variables** that are available in either condition in a specific comparison
 - For example, Condition A includes a preferred therapist and access to an **iPad** equipped with Minecraft and Condition B includes an **iPad** equipped with Minecraft.
 - The **iPad (tangible)** is the Constant Variable.

Step 4: Create COA Test Comparisons

- **Test Variables** that are available only in one condition and are isolated
 - For example, Condition A includes a **preferred therapist** and access to an iPad equipped with Minecraft and Condition B includes an iPad equipped with Minecraft.
 - The **preferred therapist (attention)** is the Test Variable.

Step 5: Select *a priori* Decision Rules and Procedures

- Determine how you will define majority for each session and whether a majority rule must be met for each session
 - For example: With a majority rule, a client must spend at least 70% in one condition otherwise the condition is repeated
- Determine how many consecutive sessions of COA pairings you will present
 - For example: We presented the same order pairing for five consecutive sessions or until the client allocated toward majority allocation for at least three consecutive sessions

Step 5: Select *a priori* Decision Rules and Procedures

- Select procedures to present, describe, and demonstrate each condition for each COA pairing
 - For example: Prior to the start of each session, explain each condition side to the client and ask if he had any questions.
- Keep procedures for presenting the COA conditions the same for each session
- Counterbalance the side for which each condition is presented
 - For example: If Condition A is presented on the right side of the room, present it on the left side of the room for the next session.

Step 6: Conduct COA Comparisons and Conduct Formative Analysis

- Following each COA comparison, make conclusions about client's responding and plan for next steps
- Conduct a formative analysis throughout the COA to make decisions about the reinforcing value of each condition
- When possible, test and make conclusions about variables (e.g., escape) in isolation prior to testing and making conclusion about synthesized variables (e.g., escape and tangible)

Step 7: Graphing, Visual Inspection, and Conclusions

- Graph the percentage of allocation or duration in s for each session
 - Use the graphing template provided in the data repository
- Identify majority allocation using visual inspection
- When differentiation occurs, make conclusions about potential choice reinforcers
- Continue the process until reinforcers have been empirically identified and could be used in a treatment

Hypothetical Case Vignettes

Client Background: Julia

- 12-year-old female diagnosed with EBD
- School setting
- Problem behavior: Disruptive behavior and low work completion
- Reason for COA: An FA is not allowed in her school setting as part of the functional behavior assessment (FBA) process

Julia (Step 2)

- Location of COA
 - Julia's classroom at her desk
- Arrangement and Choice Measurement of COA
 - Taped placed down the center of the desk with conditions signaled with placements
 - Choice measured as body allocated on either side of desk and duration of time spent on each side
- Implementers
 - Classroom teacher
- Materials
 - Items identified by teacher

Julia (Step 3)

- Using the COA Development Table (available in data repository), the BCBA identified several narrative descriptions and nominated several stimulus classes

1A: COA Development Tool for Julia

Condition	Narrative Description	Stimulus Classes	Potentially Aversive Stimuli Included?	Materials and Implementers
A	Julia does not have access to attention or tangible items. She is not expected to work.	N/A		
B	Julia is required to complete academic demands alone.		Yes	Academic work
C	Julia is required to complete academic demands but has her teacher assisting with her work.	Attention	Yes	Academic work
D	Julia has free access to preferred tangible items and activities with no attention.	Tangible		High-preferred tangibles
E	Julia has free access to preferred tangible items and activities with attention from her teacher.	Tangible, Attention		High-preferred tangibles Teacher
F	Julia has free access to attention from a preferred teacher.	Attention		Teacher
G	Julia has free access to tangible items but ones that are not as highly preferred.	Tangible		Low-preferred tangibles

Julia (Step 4)

- Using the COA Comparison and Evaluation Table, the BCBA identified relevant stimulus class including constant and test variables relevant in each condition pairing.
- Please refer to the highlighted portion on the next slide (i.e., columns 1–7) for an example. Julia's full COA Comparison and Evaluation Table can be found in the data repository.

2A: COA Comparison and Evaluation Tool for Julia

Trial	Condition	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Condition	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Constant Variables	Test Variables	Outcome	Conclusions Next Steps
1	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Repeat
2	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Repeat
3	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Escape seems valuable, Evaluate attention and escape
4	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Repeat
5	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Repeat
6	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Escape seems to be a reinforcer, Evaluate social positives to determine the role of attention and tangible
7	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Repeat
8	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Repeat

Julia (Step 5)

- Decision Rules
 - At least three consecutive sessions to demonstrate majority allocation
- Procedures
 - Julia's BCBA described each condition arrangement to her
 - Sessions were 5 min

Julia (Step 6)

- Using the COA Comparison and Evaluation Table, the BCBA took note of the majority condition allocation for each condition pairing. Please refer to the highlighted portion on the next slide (i.e., columns 8–9)
- The BCBA also took notes of any plans or relevant conclusions such as repeat the condition pairing or evaluate new condition pairings. This tool can be flexible and adapted to store ongoing observations (e.g., any instance of challenging behavior, refusal to make a choice) that might also occur. Julia's full COA Comparison and Evaluation Table can be found in the data repository.

2A: COA Comparison and Evaluation Tool for Julia

Trial	Condition	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Condition	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Constant Variables	Test Variables	Outcome	Conclusions Next Steps
1	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Repeat
2	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Repeat
3	A	Escape	B	Academic Demands		Escape	Escape	Escape seems valuable, Evaluate attention and escape
4	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Repeat
5	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Repeat
6	A	Escape	C	Academic Demands, Attention		Attention Escape	Escape	Escape seems to be a reinforcer, Evaluate social positives to determine the role of attention and tangible
7	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Repeat
8	C	Academic Demands, Attention	D	Escape, Tangible		Escape, Tangible	Escape, Tangible	Repeat

Julia (Step 7)

- Using a blank COA Graphing Template, the BCBA graphed and analyzed Julia's data.
- The BCBA concluded that Julia is sensitive to escape and assistance with the work is insufficient to maintain work completion; however, providing contingent high or low-preferred tangible items could reinforce work completion.

3A: Hypothetical COA Data for Julia

Note. A = No reinforcers or potentially aversive stimuli. B = Potentially aversive stimuli in the form of academic demands. C = Potentially aversive stimuli in the form of academic demands with teacher attention. D = Tangible. E = Tangible and attention. F = Teacher attention. G = Low-preferred tangibles.

Client Background: Avery

- 10-year-old male diagnosed with ASD and ADHD
- Clinic setting
- Problem behavior: Aggression and Property Destruction
- Reason for COA: An FA did not sufficiently evoke challenging behavior even after modification

Avery (Step 2)

- Location of COA
 - Avery's session room at his clinic
- Arrangement and Choice Measurement of COA
 - Taped placed down the center of the desk with poster boards on wall
 - Choice measured as body allocated on either side of tape and duration of time spent on each side
- Implementers
 - High and low-preferred registered behavior technicians (RBTs)
 - Caregiver
- Materials
 - Items identified by paired stimulus preference assessment

Avery (Step 3)

- Using the COA Development Table (available in data repository), the BCBA identified several narrative descriptions and nominated several stimulus classes

2A: COA Development Tool for Avery

Condition	Narrative Description	Stimulus Classes	Potentially Aversive Stimuli Included?	Materials and Implementers
A	Avery does not have access to attention or tangible items. He is not expected to work.	N/A		
B	Avery has free access to attention from the preferred RBT.	Attention		High-preferred RBT
C	Avery has free access to attention from the non-preferred RBT.	Attention	Yes	Non-preferred RBT
D	Avery is required to complete chore-like demands such as folding laundry, arranging shoes, and cleaning windows.		Yes	Chore demands
E	Avery can play games with a preferred RBT, but the RBT arranges it such that Avery is denied winning the game often.	Tangible, Attention	Yes	High-preferred tangibles High-preferred RBT
F	Avery has free access to the caregiver's attention.	Attention		Caregiver
G	Avery has free access to the RBT's attention and has free access to tangible items.	Attention Tangible		High-preferred tangibles High-preferred RBT
H	Avery has free access to preferred tangible items.	Tangible		

Avery (Step 4)

- Using the COA Comparison and Evaluation Table, the BCBA identified relevant stimulus class including constant and test variables relevant in each condition pairing.
- Please refer to the highlighted portion on the next slide (i.e., columns 1–7) for an example. Avery's full COA Comparison and Evaluation Table can be found in the data repository.

2B: COA Comparison and Evaluation Tool for Avery

Trial	Condition	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Condition	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Constant Variables	Test Variables	Outcome	Conclusions Next Steps
1	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Repeat
2	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Repeat
3	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Attention is valuable, Evaluate attention and escape
4	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Repeat
5	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Repeat
6	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Attention is valuable, Evaluate tangible
7	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Repeat
8	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Repeat
9	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Compare attention and tangible
10	B	High-preferred Attention	H	Tangible		Attention, Tangible	High-preferred Attention	Repeat

Avery (Step 5)

- Decision Rules
 - If switching occurs, repeat until three consecutive sessions of majority allocation has emerged
- Procedures
 - Avery's BCBA brings him to each side of the room allows him pre-exposure access to each side prior to selection
 - Sessions were 5 min

Avery (Step 6)

- Using the COA Comparison and Evaluation Table, the BCBA took note of the majority condition allocation for each condition pairing. Please refer to the highlighted portion on the next slide (i.e., columns 8–9)
- The BCBA also took notes of any plans or relevant conclusions such as repeat the condition pairing or evaluate new condition pairings. This tool can be flexible and adapted to store ongoing observations (e.g., any instance of challenging behavior, refusal to make a choice) that might also occur. Avery's full COA Comparison and Evaluation Table can be found in the data repository.

2B: COA Comparison and Evaluation Tool for Avery

Trial	Condition —	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Condition —	Stimulus Classes or Potentially Aversive Stimuli	Constant Variables	Test Variables	Outcome	Conclusions Next Steps
1	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Repeat
2	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Repeat
3	A	Escape	B	Attention		Attention	Attention	Attention is valuable, Evaluate attention and escape
4	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Repeat
5	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Repeat
6	A	Escape	C	Low-preferred Attention		Attention, Escape	Escape	Attention is valuable, Evaluate tangible
7	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Repeat
8	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Repeat
9	B	High-preferred Attention	G	Attention, Tangible	Attention	Tangible	Attention, Tangible	Compare attention and tangible
10	B	High-preferred Attention	H	Tangible		Attention, Tangible	High-preferred Attention	Repeat

Avery (Step 7)

- Using the COA Graphing Template, the BCBA graphed and analyzed Avery's data.
- The BCBA concluded that Avery is sensitive to attention specific types of attention and escape from non-preferred individuals and demands. The BCBA uses high-preferred attention from the RBT and caregiver as part of the intervention when presenting Avery with non-preferred demands.

3B: Hypothetical COA Data for Avery

Note. The gray bar indicates responses of challenging behavior per min scaled to the right y-axis. A = No reinforcers or potentially aversive stimuli. B = Attention (High-preferred RBT). C = Attention (Low-preferred RBT). D = Potentially aversive stimuli in the form of chore demands. E = Tangible, attention, potentially aversive stimuli in the form of loss of winning a game F = Attention (High-preferred caregiver). G = Attention and tangible. H = Tangible.

Self-Guided Assessment

Question 1

- What are the two primary reasons a COA should be considered?

Question 1

- What are the two primary reasons a COA should be considered?
- An FA does not yield differentiated results
- An FA is not possible in a given setting due to safety, policies, or concerns about expertise

Question 2

- When selecting location for a COA, I should consider:

Question 2

- When selecting location for a COA, I should consider:
- Ability to have adequate time and space in that particular location

Question 3

- Choice in a COA should be measured by:

Question 3

- Choice in a COA should be measured by:
 - Frequency of response (i.e., choice)
 - Duration of allocation (i.e., time spent in a condition)

Question 4

- How is the logic of the COA different than an FA:

Question 4

- How is the logic of the COA different than an FA:
- The FA uses comparisons between a test and control condition and determines experimental control through differentiation of responding
- The COA compares to two tests condition in a concurrent operant arrangement using a simultaneous treatment design and determines experimental control through differentiation of responding

Question 5

- What is a constant and test variable in a COA?

Question 5

- What is a control and test variable in a COA?
- A constant variable is a variable available in both conditions during a comparisons and a test variable is a variable solely isolated in one condition

Question 6

- How is tests for negative reinforcement (i.e., escape) unique in a COA?

Question 6

- How is tests for negative reinforcement (i.e., escape) unique in a COA?
- Tests are unique because the opportunity to evaluate escape solely depends on the condition comparison and the responding of the client
- When there is evidence that a client is allocating away from a potentially aversive stimulus, there is evidence for escape

Question 7

- Can COAs identify functional reinforcers for problem behavior?

Question 7

- Can COAs identify functional reinforcers for problem behavior?
- No, they can only identify reinforcers for choice behavior that could be used in a treatment for problem behavior

Question 8

- How many conditions or comparisons must be included in a COA?

Question 8

- How many conditions or comparisons must be included in a COA?
- There is no set number and should include a sufficient amount to make conclusions

Question 9

- How are COAs more favorable than indirect or descriptive data?

Question 9

- How are COAs more favorable than indirect or descriptive data?
- COAs use direct observation of choice behavior in an experimental design

Question 10

- Following graphing and conclusions from a COA, what should I do next?

Question 10

- Following graphing and conclusions from a COA, what should I do next?
- Validate the assessment outcomes through treatment or a reinforcer assessment

Application Practice

Instructions

- Use the following information and provided materials to apply and practice your learning to a hypothetical scenario.

Client Background: Lincoln

- 4-year-old male with ASD
- Emerging vocal-verbal behavior using three to four-word phrases
- Setting: Clinic
- Problem Behavior: Tantrums
- Reason for COA: An FA failed to yield differentiated outcomes
- Suspected reinforcers
 - Caregivers report that he has tantrums when he does not get his way and is told no. He likes to boss around his younger brother and gets very frustrated when his YouTube Kids channel has commercials. The caregiver suspect he wants their attention when they are giving it to his younger brother.